

YTTRIA, CERIA DOPED ZIRCONIA-ALUMINIA CERAMIC COMPOSITES FOR DENTAL APPLICATIONS

R. Lyubushkin^{1*}, O. Ivanov¹, V. Chuev², A. Buzov²

¹ Joint Research Centre “Diagnostics of structure and properties of nanomaterials”,

Belgorod State University, Belgorod, Russia

² Trading House Ltd Vladmiva, Belgorod, Russia

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1 Introduction

At present, zirconia-based ceramics are gaining popularity in dentistry, particularly in fixed prosthodontics. Clinically, it is important that ceramic restorations reproduce the translucency and color of natural teeth [1]. At ambient pressure, unalloyed zirconia can assume three crystallographic forms depending on the temperature. At room temperature and upon heating up to 1170 °C, the symmetry is monoclinic (P21/c). The structure is tetragonal (P42/nmc) between 1170 and 2370 °C and cubic (Fm⁻3m) above 2370 °C and up to the melting point [2,3]. The transformation from the tetragonal (t) phase to the monoclinic (m) phase upon cooling is accompanied by a substantial increase in volume (~4.5%), sufficient to lead to catastrophic failure. This transformation is reversible and begins at ~950 °C on cooling. Alloying pure zirconia with stabilizing oxides such as CaO, MgO, Y₂O₃ or CeO₂ allows the retention of the tetragonal structure at room temperature and therefore the control of the stress-induced t→m transformation, efficiently arresting crack propagation and leading to high toughness [1,4,5].

Zirconia based ceramics is a high performance material with excellent biocompatibility and mechanical properties, which suggest its suitability for posterior fixed partial dentures. Y₂O₃-stabilized tetragonal zirconia polycrystalline (YTZ/Al₂O₃) and CeO₂- stabilized tetragonal zirconia polycrystalline (CZA) ceramics with high-performance were prepared for dental application by use the wet chemical route, consolidated by cold isostatic pressing, and two-step sintering method. Physical and mechanical properties test results show that the bending strength, fracture toughness, and the density of full sintered ceramics suggest that the material is relatively suitable for dental restoration.

2 Experimental procedure

Aqueous solutions of Al(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, ZrO(NO₃)₂·4H₂O, Y(NO₃)₃·6H₂O and (NH₄)₂Ce(NO₃)₆ were used as the starting materials. The mixed hydrogel was obtained by adding 1:1 NH₃ solution to the mixed aqueous solution maintained at 25 °C with continuous stirring. The viscosity of the batch gradually increased and finally set to gel at pH 8.7. The gels were then aged at room temperature for 48 h. After aging, the gel was repeatedly washed with boiled distilled water to remove extraneous impurities and filtered. The filtered cake was dried at 40°C for 48 h. The synthesized specimens were characterized for specific average surface area (BET) TriStar II 3020, DTA/TG (SDT Q600) and TEM (JEM-2010). The dried gel was calcined in a muffle furnace at 700°C for 4 h in air. Samples were cold isostatic pressed at 300 MPa for 3 minutes. Subsequently two-step sintering methods were adapted for the samples. In the first step, a slow thermal debinding profile with a very slow heating rate (1 K min⁻¹ to 600°C held for 2 hours; and 5 K min⁻¹ to 1100°C held for 2 hours and 5 Kmin⁻¹ to room temperature) was carried out in Nabertherm Furnace in an atmosphere environment. In the second step, the samples were sintered in air at 1350°C for 2 hours, followed by 5 Kmin⁻¹ cooling down to room temperature. Sinterability was evaluated through the shrinkage, density value. The percent shrinkage measures the dimensional change of a sintered body from a green body, as indicated by the fractional shrinkage, $\Delta L/L_0$ in length. Specimens were characterized by XRD (Rigaku Ultima IV), AFM (Ntegra Aura), SEM (Quanta 200 3D). Mechanical properties (microhardness and fracture toughness) were measured using INSTRON Vickers microhardness-

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tester 402MVD and fracture toughness tester INSTRON 5882.

3 Results and discussion

The synthesized powder was characterized for specific average surface area (BET) and TEM (JEM-2010) was used for the determination of exact particle size. Most of the particles are spherical and in the range of 12-20 nm (Fig.1). The specific surface area of the final powders is determined by the BET surface area analysis and is calculated as 79 m²/g. The DTA/TG result indicates three-stage decomposition for pseudoboehmite and single stage decomposition for amorphous Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}O₂.

10%Al₂O₃-90%Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}O₂ powder was compacted by cold isostatic pressing of green compacts at 300 MPa and calcined. Densification studies are carried out in both the muffle furnace as well as a dilatometer in atmospheric conditions.

The sintering was carried out without any isothermal treatment with heating rate of 5 K/min. The small initial shrinkage curve up to 100°C of the compacts during sintering is responsible for the expulsion of the residual water from the sample (Fig.2). The densification starts at around 940°C. Beyond 1145°C, the slope has been changed due to completion of α-Al₂O₃. Pores are also eliminated with an achievement of 65% of the theoretical density of that particular composition. The present results exhibit the sintering without sintering additive and isothermal treatment is mainly attributed to high surface area of starting powders.

Microstructure of 10%Al₂O₃-90%Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}O₂ studied by Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) reveals that particles are present as either intergranular or intragranular in the ZrO₂ matrix. The average grain size of alumina is about 500 nm–1.5 μm and fairly homogeneous in the entire matrix. Zirconia particles are smaller in size (90–300 nm) and are isolated at grain boundaries between larger alumina grains. The microstructure of 10%Al₂O₃-90%Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}O₂ is shown in Fig. 3, in which the zirconia grains appear brighter compared to the darker alumina grains. However, the amount of porosity is greater than that of sintered Y-TZP and comprises between 8 and

11% [6]. This partially explains the generally lower mechanical properties of ceria-zirconia ceramics when compared to 3Y-TZP dental ceramics [7]. It should be pointed out, however, that Ce-Y-TZP ceramics usually exhibit better thermal stability and resistance to low temperature degradation than Y-TZP under similar thermo-cycling or aging conditions [8, 9]. It was confirmed that the Ce-Y-TZP ceramic was constituted of two crystalline phases, a rhombohedral alumina matrix (Fig.4), so-called α-alumina (R-3c, hexagonal ICDD (PDF2008) and cubic zirconia (Fm-3m ICDD (PDF2008)).

The X-ray mapping (EPMA analysis) of polished and thermally etched surface showing the presence of different elements (Al, Zr, Ce, Y) within the matrix is illustrated in Fig. 5. The EPMA analysis shows an almost uniform distribution of Y₂O₃-CeO₂-ZrO₂ in the alumina matrix. This homogeneous distribution assists to enhancement of the thermo-mechanical properties. The principal merit of the microstructure observed in the 10%Al₂O₃-90%Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}O₂ composites obtained by the chemical wet route is the adequate relative grain size ratio and phase distribution between the both phases, allowing zirconia particles to be present mostly at grain boundaries.

The mechanical properties of zirconia are the highest ever reported for any dental ceramic. This may allow the realization of posterior fixed partial dentures and permit a substantial reduction in core thickness. These capabilities are highly attractive in prosthetic dentistry, where strength and esthetics are paramount. However, due to the metastability of tetragonal zirconia, stress-generating surface treatments such as grinding or sandblasting are liable to trigger the t→m transformation with the associated volume increase leading to the formation of surface compressive stresses, thereby increasing the flexural strength but also altering the phase integrity of the material and increasing the susceptibility to aging [6]. The low temperature degradation (LTD) of zirconia is a well-documented phenomenon, exacerbated notably by the presence of water [10]. The consequences of this aging process are multiple and include surface degradation with grain pullout and microcracking as well as strength degradation.

Hardness was determined by the Vickers hardness test. Vickers hardness values were calculated using Eq. (1) where “P” was the applied load (N) and “d” was the average of the diagonal length (m) and the angle between the opposite faces of the indenter

$$H_v = \frac{\alpha P}{d^2} \quad (136^\circ)$$

Elastic modulus was determined by the resonance vibration method. Flexural strength was measured by a three-point bending test at room temperature. The tensile surfaces of the specimens were polished with a diamond liquid suspension. The span length and the cross-head speed were 30 mm and 0.5 mm/min, respectively. The fracture toughness was estimated by the indentation-fracture method with the use of the following equation of Marshall and Evans [11]:

$$K_{1c} = 0.036E^{0.4}P^{0.6}a^{-0.7}\left(\frac{c}{a}\right)^{-1.5} \quad (2),$$

where E is the elastic modulus, P is the applied load, a is the half length of the Vickers impression, and c is the half length of the median crack.

The mechanical properties of the 10% Al_2O_3 -90% $\text{Ce}_{0.1}\text{Y}_{0.1}\text{Zr}_{0.8}\text{O}_2$ nanocomposite and Y-TZP are listed in Table I. The fracture toughness of the Ce-Y-TZP/ Al_2O_3 was much higher than that Y-TZP, whereas the toughness values measured by the indentation-fracture method might be overestimated because of the rising R-curve behavior of Ce-Y-TZP/ Al_2O_3 . The alumina grains prevent nucleation of zirconia monoclinic phase and prevent transformation propagation to neighboring zirconia grains, and due to the mismatch in the elastic module between alumina and zirconia, the transformation of bulk grains becomes severely restricted. On the other hand, surface grains can accommodate such strain in a vertical direction, which may lead to grain pop-out and detachment.

4 Conclusion

This technique of preparation provides a straightforward method for the preparation of Y_2O_3 -, CeO_2 -doped ZrO_2 - Al_2O_3 nanocrystalline homogeneous solid solutions at low temperatures and for shorter annealing times, reducing segregation of the components. The mechanical properties of obtained ceramic strongly depend on its grain size. Above a critical grain size, YTZ/

Al_2O_3 is less stable and more susceptible to spontaneous $t \rightarrow m$ transformation whereas smaller grain sizes ($<1\mu\text{m}$) are associated with a lower transformation rate [12]. Moreover, below a certain grain size ($\sim 0.2\mu\text{m}$), the transformation is not possible, leading to reduced fracture toughness. Consequently, the sintering conditions have a strong impact on both stability and mechanical properties of the final product as they dictate the grain. Higher sintering temperatures and longer sintering times lead to larger grain sizes. High fracture toughness of 90% $\text{Ce}_{0.1}\text{Y}_{0.1}\text{Zr}_{0.8}\text{O}_2$ is attributed to the presence of a coupled mechanism of stress-induced transformation toughening and transformation-induced microcrack toughening, and high flexural strength of the ceramics is a coupled result of small-size flaw and high fracture toughness.

These results further indicate that the product can be used as a promising new ceramic material to fabricate dental base crowns and bridges. Composite (CZA) not only exhibited higher strength, but might also have higher fracture toughness when compared with YTZ/ Al_2O_3 .

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Fig. 1. TEM image of the 10% Al_2O_3 -90% $\text{Ce}_{0.1}\text{Y}_{0.1}\text{Zr}_{0.8}\text{O}_2$.

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Fig. 2. Sintering of a green body 10%Al₂O₃-90%Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}O₂

Fig.1. X-ray mapping (EPMA analysis) of polished and thermally etched surface 10%Al₂O₃-90%Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}O₂.

Fig. 3. Microstructure of 10%Al₂O₃-90%Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}O₂

Fig. 4. XRD pattern of 10%Al₂O₃-90%Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}O₂ sintered body sintered at 1350 °C for 2 h.

Table I. Mechanical properties of the 10%Al₂O₃-90%Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}Zr_{0.8}O₂ and Y-TZP.

	10%Al ₂ O ₃ -90%Ce _{0.1} Y _{0.1} Zr _{0.8} O	Y _{0.55} Zr _{0.93} O ₂
Flexural strength	507 ± 65 MPa	1003 ± 132 MPa
Vickers hardness <i>H_v</i>	6 GPa	13.5 GPa
Fracture toughness <i>K_{1c}</i>	8.2±0.2 MPa m ^{1/2}	6.0±0.2 MPa m ^{1/2}
Elastic modulus <i>E</i>	87 GPa	200 GPa
Thermal expansion coefficient <i>α</i>	10.1 μm/°C	10.4 μm/°C

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